

INVESTIGATION OF ORIENTATION MAGNETIC PHASE TRANSITION FOR USE IN ULTRAFAST OPTOMAGNETIC BISTABLE EFFECTS

S. A. Baranov^{1,2} and **I. I. Dobynde¹**

¹*Institute of Applied Physics, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Academiei str. 5, Chisinau, MD-2028 Republic of Moldova
E-mail: baranov@phys.asm.md*

²*Shevchenko State University, str. 25 Oktyabrya 128, Tiraspol, Republic of Moldova*

(Received December 4, 2017)

Abstract

Theoretical results of a study of the magnetization orientation phase transition in magnetically ordered cylindrical nanoparticles are described. The hysteresis dependence of equilibrium magnetization orientation X on external parameter p is derived. This hysteresis can determine the region for the observation of optical bistability in the optomagnetic inverse Faraday effect.

1. Introduction

An ultrashort laser pulse (ULP) excites the spin precession in magnetically-ordered dielectrics, as stated in [1–3]. The spin-reorientation phase transition in orthoferrites can be induced by an ULP and the rise of time of this transition is a few picoseconds [1, 2].

The femtosecond magnetization dynamics of a thin cobalt film excited with ULPs was studied using two complementary pump-probe techniques, namely, spin-, energy-, and time-resolved photoemission and the time-resolved magneto-optical Kerr effect.

Combining the two methods, it is possible to identify the microscopic electron spin-flip mechanisms responsible for the ultrafast macroscopic magnetization dynamics of the cobalt film. In particular, the authors of [1, 2] show that electron–magnon excitation does not affect the overall magnetization even though it is an efficient spin-flip channel on the sub-200 fs time scale. Instead, we find an experimental evidence for the relevance of Elliott–Yafet-type spin-flip processes for the ultrafast demagnetization taking place on a time scale of 300 fs.

A typical experimental geometry is schematically shown in Fig. 1 (see [1–3]).

Fig. 1. Example of experimental geometry [1–3].

2. Model Cylindrical Nanoparticles and Calculation Method

The Landau–Lifshits equation-based description of the reorientation phase transitions dynamics was considered (see [4–7]):

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = -\gamma_0 M \times H_{\text{eff}} + \alpha M \times \frac{dM}{dt} \quad , \quad (1)$$

where M is the saturation magnetization, γ_0 is the gyromagnetic ratio, H_{eff} determined as a anisotropy field (about H_{eff} and free energy $F(\Psi)$, see below), and α is the Gilbert damping parameter.

A simple version of anisotropy energy is presented in the following form:

$$F_{em} = -\frac{3}{2} \lambda \sigma \cos^2(\psi - \psi_0) \quad . \quad (2)$$

Then, for magnetic permeability μ , the following could be obtained:

$$\mu = \left(\frac{3\lambda\sigma}{M^2} - N_{\Delta} \right)^{-1} \quad . \quad (3)$$

The above equation was derived in terms of the orientation phase transition theory.

However, in the case where F_{ms} and F_{em} compensate for each other, the expansion term F_{em} should be considered; it can be expressed in the following form:

$$F_2 = K_2 \cos^4(\psi - \psi_0) \quad . \quad (4)$$

The form of function F_2 for orientation change of phase in crystalloid magnetic depends on the type symmetry of the crystal; equation (4) corresponds to a hexagonal symmetry. The form of the above function for amorphous materials is not exactly known; therefore, further calculations of quality are only calculations of free energy and should also contain the F_H field term and have the following form:

$$F_H = -MH \cos \psi \quad (5)$$

and

$$F = F_{ms} + F_H + F_{em} + F_2 \quad . \quad (6)$$

Equilibrium orientation of magnetization is deducted from the solution for the equation obtained from the following:

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \psi} = 0 \quad \text{provided that} \quad \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial^2 \psi} \geq 0 \quad . \quad (7)$$

For the relative magnetization along microwire axis $X = \cos \psi$, a numerical solution could be obtained. For quality assessment, the equation could be simplified if we assume that

$$F_{em} + F_{ms} = K_1 \cos^2(\psi - \psi_0) \quad , \quad (8)$$

and

$$F_2 = K_2 \cos^4 \psi \quad . \quad (9)$$

In the case where $\psi_0 \approx \pi/2$, the equation will acquire the following form:

$$4gX^3 + 2X + p = 0, \quad (10)$$

$$\text{where } g = \frac{K_2}{K_1} \text{ and } p = \frac{MH}{K_1}.$$

Parameter p characterizes the applied field, while parameter g characterizes the relation of the anisotropy constants, where the g value significantly increases near the “compensation” point due to the fact that K_1 tends to zero.

The generalized coordinate $\sin^2 \psi$ expansion was used for the free energy representation:

$$F = F_0 + K_1(T) \sin^2 \psi + K_2 \sin^4 \psi \quad (11)$$

The summand, which is proportional to the value of $\{H(t)M \sin \Psi\}$ and corresponds to the interreaction with the field, enters the F_0 term.

Parameter Ψ is the angle between the magnetization vector and the anisotropy axis and the external field $H(t)$.

In the elementary case, the direction of the $H(t)$ vector coincides with the axis of all anisotropies; coefficients $K_1(T)$ and K_2 are the scalar parameters of these anisotropies; a change in them initiates the onset of reorientation phase transitions.

3. Results and Discussion

Let us consider the following expansion of the free energy:

$$F = F_0 + K_1(T) \cos^2(\psi - \psi_0) + K_2 \cos^4 \psi \quad (12)$$

The free energy representation is attributed to the fact the anisotropy axes would be probably nonparallel to one another in the general case. Equilibrium magnetization orientation $X = \cos \psi$ is determined by expression (13):

$$\begin{aligned} & -16 \cdot g^2 \cdot X^8 + (16 \cdot g^2 - 16 \cdot p \cdot g \cdot \cos 2\psi_0) \cdot X^6 - 8 \cdot p \cdot g \cdot X^5 + \\ & + (16 \cdot p \cdot g \cdot \cos 2\psi_0 - 4) \cdot X^4 + (8 \cdot p \cdot g - 4 \cdot p \cdot \cos 2\psi_0) \cdot X^3 + (4 - p^2) \cdot X^2 + \\ & + 4 \cdot p \cdot \cos 2\psi_0 \cdot X + p^2 - \sin^2 2\psi_0 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $p = MH/K_1$ and $g = K_2/K_1$.

We derived the hysteresis dependence of the X value on external parameter p from expression (13) (see Figs. 2, 3).

Fig. 2. Examples of numerical solutions for expression (13) for $g = 0.1$ and $g = -1$.

Fig. 3. Examples of numerical solutions for expression (13) for $g = -1$ and $\langle\langle K_2 \rangle\rangle = -100$.

4. Conclusions

It has been analytically shown that experimental data described in [1–3] can be interpreted as magnetization orientation phase transitions in magnetically ordered cylindrical nanoparticles [4–7]. This result can determine the region for the observation of optical bistability in the optomagnetic inverse Faraday effect [1, 2].

References

- [1] A.M. Kalashnikova, A.V. Kimel', and R.V. Pisarev, *Usp. Fiz. Nauk* 185, 1054 (2015).
- [2] A.V. Kimel and A.K. Zvezdin, *Low Temp. Phys.* 41, 878 (2015).
- [3] A.P. Pyatakov, A.S. Sergeev, E.P. Nikolaeva, T.B. Kosykh, A.V. Nikolaev, K.A. Zvezdin, and A.K. Zvezdin, *Usp. Fiz. Nauk* 185, 1078 (2015).
- [4] H. Horner and C.M. Varma, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 20, 845 (1968).
- [5] L.D. Landau and E.M. Lifshits, *Elektrodinamika sploshnykh sred*, Nauka, Moscow, 1982.
- [6] K.P. Belov, A.K. Zvezdin, A.M. Kadomtsev, and R.Z. Levitin, *Usp. Fiz. Nauk* 119, 447 (1976).
- [7] V.G. Bar'yakhtar, A.N. Bogdanov, and D.A. Yablonskii, *Usp. Fiz. Nauk* 156, 47 (1988).